

FASHION aLIVE

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Executive Summary

This report demonstrates the publication of the digital engagement strategies (videos for video-mapping, light shows and concept videos), developed by each partner to highlight their collections' showcase, in the project website and social media.

Introduction

Digital engagement strategies are a central part of the storytelling plan put into place the project partners Creamodite, Uminho, and Ucampania, to highlight each partner's collection's message and aid in creating memorable performance runway events to help spread the message about the importance of sustainable fashion.

Each partner envisioned a digital engagement strategy that would enhance their take on sustainable fashion:

- CREAMODITE designed a futuristic light-show to accompany the performance's tempo and music whilst translating their Zero Waste Fashion's collection avant-garde feel and look into transforming the classical look of the selected venue, Ateneo de Madrid, into a "futuristic space-ship" of sorts.
- UMINHO skilfully applied their digital engagement strategy design to intervene the location of the fashion-show, using LED walls as a background for the models to emerge from, complimented by ephemeral architecture installations on the floor. The overall message delivered by their strategy was to raise awareness on discarded garment dumping into landfills, establishing upcycling as a useful solution to this issue.
- UCAMPANIA intervened Convento di San Lorenzo ad Septimum's cloister with a videomapping installation on two of the four walls that made up the stage, in addition to an LED wall, creating an ambiance that enhanced the collection's theme of slow fashion and Italy's rich cultural tradition of corredo reimagined, through animations and text designed to fit the particularities of the venue and its main architectural features.

Videos and images were uploaded to the project website and social media, with the aim of generating further dissemination of the importance of sustainable fashion promotion; as well as establishing digital engagement strategies as an aid in creating engaging and innovative performance runway events that create a lasting impact on the audience, and in the Fashion Alive project's case, help disseminate each partner's take on sustainable fashion.

Project website

Digital engagement strategies were showcased in the project website via the use of a blog post, aimed at explaining the project's take on sustainable fashion communication by planning events through a storytelling lens, and incorporating digital engagement strategies as a fundamental part of raising awareness through cultural and creative expression.

Moreover, the post includes a summary of each partner's collection inspiration and the digital engagement strategy developed in accordance. The structure of the post includes an overview of the project's mission and storytelling plans, and later delves into each partner's adaptation, culminating with the videos of each digital engagement strategy embedded onto the post.

Available at: <https://fashion-alive.com/digital-engagement-strategies>

GOING GREEN, GOING DIGITAL

THE KEY TO SUSTAINABLE FASHION'S SUCCESS!

31.07.2023

Through avant-garde showcases and digital engagement strategies, Fashion Alive seeks to inspire and captivate audiences, encouraging them to embrace conscious fashion choices and become part of the movement for a more sustainable fashion industry.

STORYTELLING FOR EVENT PLANNING

Imagine a world where words weave magical tales, where stories come alive through various artistic expressions – from spoken word to film, theater, and visual arts. This enchanting art, known as storytelling, goes far beyond entertainment; it holds the key to education, cultural preservation, and even social change. Within the heart of Fashion Alive, storytelling emerges as a transformative force, inspiring, challenging perspectives, and uniting diverse audiences in a shared vision of sustainable fashion.

As we step into the realm of Fashion Alive events, the power of storytelling takes center stage. Like a finely crafted thread, it weaves together the values and principles of sustainable fashion, forming an irresistible narrative that captivates and connects every soul attending these remarkable gatherings. Prepare to be spellbound as our partners bring forth a compelling story that resonates deeply with your heart, igniting a passion for a fashion world that embraces consciousness and compassion.

DIGITAL ENGAGEMENT STRATEGIES

Storytelling serves to illustrate the broader narrative of fast fashion's impact on the planet as well as sustainable fashion's contribution to a better and brighter future. Through compelling narratives, event planners balance raising awareness about the detrimental effects of fast fashion, such as waste generation and pollution, with the sustainable design solutions that show promise in building a path for a more sustainable fashion industry.

By presenting these issues in a storytelling format, attendees are more likely to grasp the urgency and become motivated to support sustainable alternatives.

The sum of these elements is translated into digital engagement strategies designed to create a dynamic and impactful approach, engaging audiences in the realm of sustainability. Each partner tackled different symbolic aspects of sustainable fashion based on their collections' findings, using visual displays, videos, and interactive exhibits to create immersive experiences that complement the collections.

ZERO WASTE FASHION

Zero Waste Fashion represents the forefront of sustainable production methods, because it prevents waste generation from the start via creative design strategies.

The result is a versatile, genderless collection of sustainable garments that balance sharp geometric edges with more soft and deconstructed volumes, materialized in all black fabric, conveying a modern, avant-garde look.

To communicate this, Creamodite based their concept on exploiting the tension between the classical, historic look of Ateneo de Madrid and the modern feel of the collection as a symbol for change and the need to break with conventional patterns to advance sustainability in the fashion industry.

This translated into a digital engagement strategy in the form of a futuristic neon-light show that transforms the classical stage into a futuristic space, creating an environment that represents the avant-garde look and feel of the collection.

CIRCULAR FASHION AND UPCYCLING

Uminho set out to develop a collection that re-signifies unused and forgotten garments in their student's closets, making them desirable again by upcycling into new pieces whilst respecting the essence and men UModa | Fashion Alive to the original garment, which add value.

This resulted in a joyful, colourful collection achieved through the combination of pre-used garments, where control over the colour palette is at best limited.

To build a narrative that replays the doomsday journey of most clothes that end up in landfills, re-playing the ending to convey a message of hope for the future in the promise of upcycling. The tension is created by presenting the problem of landfills, literally portrayed in the digital engagement strategy, and reinforced by ephemeral architecture.

Therefore, the high-point of the digital engagement strategy consisted of an introductory concept video that informs the audience of the detrimental effects of fast fashion on the environment, which later mutates into a concept video played in the background while the performance takes place, where the performers will interact with the ephemeral architecture on the floor intervening the space and mimicking waste piles, albeit illuminated by bright colourful lights; and resolved through a joyful, upbeat performance.

CULTURAL HERITAGE AND SUSTAINABLE FASHION

Unicompania developed a collection based on re-signifying corredo, through the lens of slow fashion and aimed at a hybridisation of craft techniques, advanced production processes and upcycling to give it new meaning. The end result is a sophisticated collection in all-white, with red and blue accents, that tap into Italy's made-in phenomenon by exhibiting a sense of style, sophistication and history embued in every design.

Creating a dialogue between cultural heritage and slow fashion with modern, accelerated times, Unicompania based their event concept in examining their coexistence by hybridizing advanced digital techniques and valuable historic traditions portrayed in the designs, to showcase the appeal of individuality and context for sustainable design.

It was presented in a way that emphasizes how cultural heritage is and must be a part of a sustainable fashion future:

The cloister was intervened with a videomapping projection on the floor of the patio, taking advantage of the space and enriching the experience. Said videomapping incorporated elements of the collection, playing with clocks and lines as a way to symbolize slow fashion. The concept was aided by the addition of an LED wall showcasing concept videos that illustrate the message of the collection.

In all three events, digital engagement strategies were skillfully employed to create a dynamic and impactful approach, immersing audiences in the realm of sustainability.

Each partner tackled different symbolic aspects of sustainable fashion, drawing from their collections' findings and utilizing visual displays, videos, and interactive exhibits to create mesmerizing experiences that beautifully complemented their creations.

Overall, we firmly believe that weaving storytelling into a multi-disciplinary approach, fusing technology, innovation, arts, and fashion, would captivate attendees and inspire them to question traditional norms while exploring new possibilities for a more sustainable fashion industry.

The culmination of these factors therefore set Fashion Alive events apart from conventional fashion shows, introducing innovations that established a profound and lasting bond with the audience, leaving them enchanted and ready to embrace a brighter future of conscious fashion.

Stay tuned for more updates and backstage content from the shows while we wait for the official Fashion Alive Fashion film, coming soon...

SPREAD THE WORD

Social media dissemination

Additionally, snapshots of the digital engagement strategies were adapted into social media post formats as videos and photographs fitting requirements for Instagram, Facebook and YouTube.

Instagram

https://www.instagram.com/p/Csq4zJboZmn/?img_index=1

<https://www.instagram.com/p/CtkEtUngqFE/>

<https://www.instagram.com/p/CvCqM1zoPbV/>

https://www.instagram.com/p/CtZzak5L5fm/?img_index=1

https://www.instagram.com/p/Cu6tbk9IHwO/?img_index=1

<https://www.instagram.com/p/CtgINoPKU2s/>

YouTube

FASHION ALIVE 2023 PASARELA COMPLETA

Creamodite Asociación
9.15 K suscriptores

Suscrito

4

Compartir

Compartir

Descargar

Recortar

...

60 vistas hace 1 mes #sustainablefashion #performance #zero

Creamodite's research on sustainable fashion will be presented in a runway-performance format on May 19, 2023 at El Ateneo in Madrid. It will not be a conventional fashion show, in which models simply parade designs on a catwalk. Instead, it will be a performance that deconstructs the traditional catwalk concept, by incorporating street performers, dancers and a lightshow performance installation. This results in a disruptive and innovative visual display, channeling the power of artistic expression as an engine for change in society. . #fashionalive #zerowaste #zerowastefashion #perform: Mostrar más

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=IESKZj9WvTQ&t=20s&ab_channel=CreamoditeAsociaci%C3%B3n

UModa | Fashion Alive

UMODA
198 suscriptores

Suscribirse

47

Compartir

Compartir

Descargar

Guardar

...

1 K vistas Transmitido hace 1 mes

Os estudantes de Design e Marketing de Moda da Universidade do Minho (UMinho) apresentam as suas coleções de final de curso num desfile agendado para esta sexta-feira, dia 2, às 21h30, no Instituto de Design de Guimarães. Nesta oitava edição do evento "UModa", também com transmissão no YouTube, os jovens criativos dão a conhecer cerca de 80 looks inéditos para os segmentos casual, urbano, cocktail e conceptual, com peças de vestuário e acessórios. Mostrar más

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=WMLbDLmGSX8&t=140s&ab_channel=UMODA

Fashion Alive.

V: **unicampania**
2.46 K suscriptores

Suscribirse

Me gusta

Compartir

Descargar

Recortar

416 vistas Transmitido hace 3 semanas

Finanziato dalla Comunità Europea, il progetto Fashion Alive, condiviso con un team internazionale che include Creamodite, Asociación para la constitución y reestructuración de empresas de moda diseño y tecnología, di Madrid, e l'Universidade do Minho, Departamento de Engenharia Têxtil, di Guimarães, in Portogallo, è finalizzato alla diffusione e sperimentazione di pratiche e metodi sostenibili nell'industria della moda. In tal senso, il contributo portato avanti dal gruppo di ricerca - e assunto come tema d'anno da molti insegnamenti dei Corsi di laurea in Design per la Moda e Design. [Mostrar más](#)

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=XS-B6jLPXY8&ab_channel=unicampania

Facebook

Fashion Alive
11 de junio · 🌐

On the way to making the fashion industry more sustainable, we created a fashion show focused on upcycling. This method assigns value and opportunity to end-of-life clothing. It is taking unused pieces and transforming them into something exclusive and unique. Thank you for watching our fashion show! You can watch it as many times as you want on the @umoda_ youtube channel.

[#sustainability](#) [#runwayshow](#) [#fashionalive](#) [#upcycling](#) [#runway](#)

📣 Promociona esta publicación para llegar a 1840 personas más por €14. [Promocionar publicación](#)

👍 Gisela Beatriz Fortuna Mantellini y 8 personas más

👍 Me gusta 💬 Comentar ➦ Compartir 🌐

 Fashion Alive está en **Ateneo de Madrid**.
25 de mayo · Madrid, Comunidad de Madrid · 🌐

THE POWER OF PERFORMANCE | Zero Waste Fashion represents the forefront of sustainability. To convey this message, we decided to break the barriers of the traditional runway to communicate in a striking way. Our performance goes beyond clothing: it is an artistic expression that blends fashion, visual art, and contemporary dance. In the iconic Ateneo de Madrid, we created a retro-futuristic light show that transformed the classical architecture of the theater. Models and dance... [Ver más](#)

 Promociona esta publicación para llegar a 1840 personas más por €14. [Promocionar publicación](#)

 Gisela Beatriz Fortuna Mantellini y 5 personas más 2 veces compartido

One Look
Reels · 23 de jul · 🌐

*... e scure
... e propria
... e disaccare le tradizioni di famiglia*

Premiar

FASHION ALIVE ✨ Finanziato dalla Comunità Europea e condiviso con un team internazionale Creamodite (Madrid), e l'Universidade do Minho (Portogallo), ... Ver más

🔊 One Look · Audio original

One Look
Reels · 23 de jul · 🌐

visioni di famiglia *strutturare e abitare* *la*
memorie culturali *capacità e volontà di tutto ciò che*

Premiar
1

FASHION ALIVE ✨ Finanziato dalla Comunità Europea e condiviso con un team internazionale Creamodite (Madrid), e l'Universidade do Minho (Portogallo), ... Ver más

🔊 audio original One Look

One Look
Reels · 23 de jul · 🌐

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One Look · Audio orig

Premiar

2